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*Archaeological Results of Responsible Metal Detecting in
Cooperation with Museums: Evidence from Békés County,
Hungary¹*

Museum-coordinated metal detecting in Békés County (southeastern Hungary)—similarly to developments elsewhere in Hungary—began in the early 2000s. At present, amateur metal detectorists collaborate with three museums holding officially designated archaeological collecting mandates. After a general overview of this form of cooperation, this paper focuses on the methods and practical experiences of the Munkácsy Mihály Museum in Békéscsaba.

Metal Detecting and Archaeology in the Past

In 1941, the Hungarian News Agency reported that physicians in Berlin had invented a metal-detecting probe capable of audibly indicating the location of foreign metallic objects within the human body (*Zimmer 1941*). The first Hungarian-developed detector suitable for metal detection was based on a patent by Ferenc Csanda, Lajos Molnár, and Tibor Zalavári; its primary purpose was the identification of underground utility lines (*MTI 1961; Csanda 1972*).

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The device was first employed in an archaeological context in December 1963, in connection with coins discovered at Hódmezővásárhely-Szikáncs, including issues of Theodosius II and Valentinian III (*Korek 1963:294; Korek 1964:56–57*). In 1974, reports appeared on the use of handheld metal detectors by socialist police forces (Pless 1974:7). In 1980, such an instrument was also displayed in an exhibition at the Hungarian National Gallery (“A Múzsák kertje közelről”–*E. Török 1980:180*).

Although certain museums had already possessed metal detectors from the 1960s–1970s onward (for example, the Coin Collection of the Hungarian National Museum, as well as institutions in Kecskemét), the majority acquired such equipment only from the 1990s. In the early period, the Coin Collection of the Hungarian National Museum provided assistance to regional museums, as documented in numerous contemporary reports. During the archaeological investigations conducted along the space of the M43 motorway, a 2009 publication still presented the use of metal-detecting equipment as a novel methodological element (*Balogh 2009:2*).

During the 1990s, private individuals acting as metal-detecting collectors also came into contact with the museum in Békéscsaba. In 1994, this cooperation led to the recovery of Early Iron Age finds from the outskirts of Sarkadkeresztúr (*Gyucha 1996:67–127*), while at a later date an individual described as “an informant long interested in archaeological finds” discovered a Late Gothic candlestick in the vicinity of Sarkad (*Szatmári 2003:387*).

Local daily newspapers had already informed the general public about the usefulness of metal detectors in archaeology during the 1980s. At that time, the prevailing practice consisted of targeted searches and on-site inspections following find notifications; as a result, coin finds and coin

hoards were most commonly incorporated into museum collections. Across Hungary, a renewed fascination with ancient treasure hunting emerged, in connection with which Szende László published an engaging study entitled “*A kincskereső műszer és a leletbejelentés (The Treasure-Hunting Device and Find Reporting–Szende 2006:37–42).*”

In 1996, Fehér József, in connection with the Bodrogolaszi hoard, already raised the issue that “illegal archaeologists” made use of metal detectors—primarily abroad (*Fehér 1996:137*). From the 2000s onward, museum publications themselves increasingly reported that certain sites were regularly frequented by detectorists (e.g., Tata–Ipari park; site surveys conducted by Kisné Cseh Julianna and Petényi Sándor, 2001–*Kisné and Petényi 2004:20*).

From the 1990s, the use of metal detectors immediately prior to the commencement of excavations became a recurrent practice in Hungarian archaeology (for example, Töltéstava–Alsótáplány dűlő, Győr-Moson-Sopron County, 1991; excavation directed by Gabriella Gabrieli–*Gabrieli 1993:46, 68*). Nationwide, it gradually became standard practice to employ metal detectors in cases where excavation was not possible, as well as during find mapping and collection, site prospection, the screening of excavated soil deposits (spoil heaps), and for post-excavation control purposes. In metal-detector surveys, it is frequently observed that only plowsoil yields dispersed finds, while no material is recovered from deeper layers. In addition, the use of metal detectors provided new momentum for battlefield research conducted in conjunction with systematic field surveys (*Négyesi 2015:392*).

...and in the Present

With regard to metal-detecting–based research, a generally accepted terminology is still in the process of formation, just as a wide range of designations is used for those who engage in this activity illegally. The latter group poses a particular threat to archaeological sites in Békés County, which are especially vulnerable in this respect.

Individuals engaged in illegal activities often have access to a range of professional aids that facilitate the looting and disturbance of archaeological sites. This is partly due to the fact that the archaeological topography of certain areas of the county is freely accessible (Magyarország Régészeti Topográfiája [*Archaeological Topography of Hungary*], vols. 6, 8, and 10), while the map appendices of various monographs also reveal the locations of sites from different archaeological periods (Szatmári 2005).

At the same time, it must not be overlooked that there are committed local patriots, amateur local historians, and hobbyists who are not only willing to cooperate with professional archaeologists but are also capable of contributing meaningfully to the professional work of museums. The successful outcomes of such collaborations are demonstrated by the practices of several museums (Rácz 2017). At the same time, it is evident that the problems inherent in this field engage the archaeological profession not only in neighboring countries but also in Denmark, Germany, and Great Britain (Thomas 2012).

At present, three museums holding officially designated archaeological collecting mandates cooperate with museum-affiliated metal detectorists in Békés County. At the Nagy Gyula Territorial Museum, such cooperation is linked primarily to independently conducted research projects. In Gyula, the Erkel Ferenc Cultural Center and Museum has engaged in collaboration in connection with excavations carried out at the castle (Papp 2015).

The Munkácsy Mihály Museum, by contrast, initiated cooperation during trial trenching and preventive excavations conducted along the route of the M44 expressway. In addition, collaboration with hobby metal detectorists was also established as part of a *csárda* research project—*csárda* being a traditional Hungarian roadside inn—aimed at documenting local material culture of the 18th–19th centuries (Nagy-Laczkó 2018:11). The methods applied and the experiences gained through these forms of cooperation are summarized below.

Experiences and Results

During the preventive excavations conducted in 2017 along the M44 expressway on the Tizsakürt–Kondoros section, archaeologists of the Munkácsy Mihály Museum had their first opportunity to directly involve metal detectorists working under contract with the museum. As an initial step, immediately prior to mechanical topsoil stripping, the areas of the sites affected by the road construction were jointly surveyed together with the detectorists.

During these surveys, artifact material was identified at several locations both on the surface and in its immediate vicinity—material that would likely have been lost through conventional research methods or during mechanical stripping. The recovered finds were documented following the standard procedures applied in systematic fieldwalking. Based on these experiences, it can be stated that the effectiveness of pre-stripping metal-detector surveys is strongly influenced by surface conditions. Tall or dense ground vegetation, as well as high stubble remaining from monoculture crops (such as maize, wheat, sunflower, or soybean), can significantly hinder or even render impossible the effective “sweeping” of handheld detectors. Weather conditions likewise play an important role,

as soil moisture content directly affects the reliability and performance of the devices.

Following mechanical stripping, individual test trenches were also examined using metal detectors. During this phase, locations where the machinery had produced signals were marked; however, in contrast to the collection of pre-stripping surface finds, further investigation at these points was conducted using traditional excavation methods in order to avoid information loss resulting from the disturbance of archaeological features. During both preventive and trial excavations—at sites including cemeteries and settlements of various chronological periods—metal-detecting surveys were repeatedly carried out. The excavated soil (spoil heaps) from both trenches and individual features was screened multiple times with detectors, and already exposed archaeological features were also checked as a form of control. An important observation was that the devices used by hobby detectorists often failed to detect heavily corroded, small-sized metal objects—primarily bronze dress accessories, such as belt fittings from Late Avar graves.

In connection with both the excavations mentioned above and the csárda research projects it is also important to highlight another factor influencing metal-detecting surveys: modern and recent contamination. Patterns of modern debris clearly delineate former, non-archaeological-period farmsteads and dirt roads. Proximity to roads, in particular, generates substantial “noise” at archaeological sites. Given that signals produced by modern materials and archaeological artifacts are often difficult or impossible to distinguish using the available equipment, such surveys currently involve a considerable amount of unproductive effort, resulting in the recovery of large quantities of beer cans and soft-drink caps. A small consolation is that these same disturbing factors also tend to discourage illegal metal detectorists. In

Békés County, many of the csárdas included in research remained in operation well into the 20th century, functioning as stopping places or even family residences; the resulting level of modern disturbance has long deterred illicit treasure hunters in the region.

Beyond the results of the surveys themselves, one of the most significant benefits of involving local amateur metal detectorists is the strengthening of museum–community relations. Bringing heritage protection and archaeological practice closer to local residents fosters a sense of shared ownership over cultural heritage and local history—an engagement far deeper than that achieved through academic publications or news reports, which often fail to reach the wider public. Museum-affiliated metal detecting also offers important and still underexploited opportunities in public outreach and education, particularly in relation to community archaeology, which remains in an early stage of development in Hungary. Improving relationships with local communities is therefore of decisive importance for the future of heritage protection in the country.

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